

Supplemental Information:

Challenges in Cooperative Coevolution of Physically Heterogeneous Robot Teams

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1 Choice of Representative in Fitness-driven Coevolution

Two approaches were evaluated for the choice of representative individual in fitness-driven cooperative coevolution:

Best The highest-fitness individual of the previous generation is chosen as the population representative.

Random One randomly chosen individual from the current population is chosen as the representative.

The results are reported in Figure 1 and Figure 2. 15 independent evolutionary runs were performed for the *Random* strategy, for each task variant, and 30 evolutionary runs for the *Best* strategy. The results show that the *Best* strategy significantly outperforms or matches the *Random* strategy in all the task variants.

2 Choice of Representative in Multi-Objective Algorithms

Four approaches were evaluated for the choice of the representative individual in the methods that employed multi-objectivisation (MOEA and NS):

Best The highest-fitness individual of the previous generation is chosen as the population representative.

Random One randomly chosen individual from the current population is chosen as the representative.

Pareto One randomly chosen individual belonging to the first (non-dominated) pareto front is used as the representative of the population.

Max The individuals that obtained the highest scores in each of the objectives are chosen as the representatives of the population. When the same individual obtained the highest scores for all objectives, only that individual is chosen as the representative. Multiple collaborations can thus be used to evaluate each individual. The individuals are scored according to the collaboration that achieved the highest fitness score (number of items collected).

The results are presented in Figure 3, Figure 4, and Listing 1. 30 independent evolutionary runs were performed for the *Best* strategy, for each task variant, and 15 evolutionary runs for each of the other strategies. The results show that the *Best* strategy is overall the highest performing strategy. For both the MOEA and NS approaches, the *Best* strategy is never significantly outperformed by the other strategies ($p < 0.05$, Mann-Whitney U test) in all task variants.

3 Variability of the Average Behaviour

To better understand the variability of the average behaviour of the *best-of-generation* teams, we individually plotted 10 randomly chosen runs. The plots show the behaviour of the *best-of-generation* team over the generations, for each of those evolutionary runs. The *best-of-generation* team is the team that obtained the highest fitness score in a given generation, and the behaviour is measured according to the number of items collected by that team, and fraction of time the aerial and ground robots spent within the sensing range of one another (*time within range*). The results are shown Figures 5–9.

Figure 1: Boxplots of the highest fitness score achieved in each evolutionary run, comparing the different representative selection strategies. Comparing both strategies with the Mann-Whitney U test, the following p-values were calculated: 0.044 (Fix-Tog), 0.981 (Fix-Sep), 0.007 (Var-Tog), 0.002 (Var-Mid), 1.5e-06 (Var-Sep).

Figure 2: Highest fitness score achieved until each generation.

Figure 3: Boxplots of the highest fitness score achieved in each evolutionary run, comparing the different representative selection strategies.

Figure 4: Highest fitness score achieved until each generation, averaged over 15 evolutionary runs for each evolutionary setup.

Listing 1: Statistical tests for the strategies of selecting population representatives. Two-sided Mann-Whitney U tests, with the p-values adjusted using the Holm-Bonferroni correction, and Kruskal-Wallis tests.

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### Fix-Sep MOEA ###

      Best      Max      Pareto      Random
Best      NA 0.79863610 0.4063262 0.13784994
Max      0.7986361      NA 0.1948564 0.03059473
Pareto 0.4063262 0.19485642      NA 0.96690374
Random 0.1378499 0.03059473 0.9669037      NA

Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 9.5452, df = 3, p-value = 0.02286

### Fix-Sep NS ###

      Best      Max      Pareto      Random
Best      NA 0.001995039 0.08574681 0.647260140
Max      0.001995039      NA 0.17010056 0.004983512
Pareto 0.085746808 0.170100559      NA 0.153485433
Random 0.647260140 0.004983512 0.15348543      NA

Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 18.005, df = 3, p-value = 0.0004388

### Var-Tog MOEA ###

      Best      Max      Pareto      Random
Best      NA 0.011080688 7.671559e-05 4.737253e-06
Max      1.108069e-02      NA 5.564129e-02 9.806564e-03
Pareto 7.671559e-05 0.055641288      NA 3.946317e-01
Random 4.737253e-06 0.009806564 3.946317e-01      NA

Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 36.997, df = 3, p-value = 4.607e-08

### Var-Tog NS ###

      Best      Max      Pareto      Random
Best      NA 0.2148443 0.43763498 0.0002953495
Max      0.2148443172      NA 0.49324885 0.2148443172
Pareto 0.4376349850 0.4932488      NA 0.0149231129
Random 0.0002953495 0.2148443 0.01492311      NA

Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 18.576, df = 3, p-value = 0.0003345

### Var-Mid MOEA ###

      Best      Max      Pareto      Random
Best      NA 0.161582786 0.0001187411 3.587841e-05
Max      1.615828e-01      NA 0.0571495176 8.550839e-03
Pareto 1.187411e-04 0.057149518      NA 2.714277e-01
Random 3.587841e-05 0.008550839 0.2714277115      NA

Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 31.68, df = 3, p-value = 6.112e-07

### Var-Mid NS ###

      Best      Max      Pareto      Random
Best      NA 7.809628e-05 0.07289049 0.0002229698
Max      7.809628e-05      NA 0.08808140 0.0880813991
Pareto 7.289049e-02 8.808140e-02      NA 0.0190853920
Random 2.229698e-04 8.808140e-02 0.01908539      NA

Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 29.883, df = 3, p-value = 1.461e-06

### Var-Sep MOEA ###

      Best      Max      Pareto      Random
Best      NA 0.4585102 0.3449957 0.2170682
Max      0.4585102      NA 0.9612669 0.8974990
Pareto 0.3449957 0.9612669      NA 0.9612669
Random 0.2170682 0.8974990 0.9612669      NA

Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 6.8741, df = 3, p-value = 0.07602

### Var-Sep NS ###

      Best      Max      Pareto      Random
Best      NA 0.2092930 0.2545704 0.07867833
Max      0.20929305      NA 0.7399381 0.35916219
Pareto 0.25457040 0.7399381      NA 0.35916219
Random 0.07867833 0.3591622 0.3591622      NA

Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 9.924, df = 3, p-value = 0.01922

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Figure 5: Behaviour of the *best-of-generation* teams from evolutionary runs of **fitness-driven cooperative coevolution (Fit)**.

Figure 6: Behaviour of the *best-of-generation* teams from evolutionary runs of **incremental evolution (Inc)**.

Figure 7: Behaviour of the *best-of-generation* teams from evolutionary runs of **non-cooperative incremental evolution (NInc)**.

Figure 8: Behaviour of the *best-of-generation* teams from evolutionary runs of **multi-objectivisation of sub-goals (MOEA)**.

Figure 9: Behaviour of the *best-of-generation* teams from evolutionary runs of **novelty-driven cooperative coevolution (NS)**.